

MONITORING THE PROCESS OF «LEADING A HEALTHY LIFESTYLE» AMONG STUDENTS OF THE TASHKENT MEDICAL ACADEMY.

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Summary: The article deals with some of the topical issues of protection and promotion of human health. It is well known that a healthy lifestyle is the key to a long life. After all, each of us, in the first place, should think about our health. Thus, we will live a prosperous life and prevent many difficult diseases. To this end, we have monitored the improvement of the quality and effectiveness of student learning by "promoting the principles of a healthy lifestyle and physical activity, increasing the health index and eliminating health problems."

Keywords: *health, physical culture and sports, healthy lifestyle.*

Relevance of the topic. In the normative legal documents adopted in our republic on reforming healthcare and the sphere of physical culture and sports, along with the improvement of these systems, great importance is attached to the formation of a healthy lifestyle among the population as one of the important directions of state policy in this area.

[1]

In particular, they approved and aimed at implementing the concept of development of the health care system: physical culture and sports of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2025, prevention of non-communicable diseases until 2022, support of a healthy lifestyle and increasing the level of physical activity of the population. As well as measures have been approved for the wide introduction of a healthy lifestyle and the further development of mass sports [3]. *According to the health organization, the lag in rational growth and mental development in young people is caused by non-compliance with the norms and rules of physical activity, nutrition, excessive consumption of foods high in salt, sugar, fat, as well as insufficient intake of vitamins and minerals. In adults, this behavior can cause the development of a number of diseases of the cardiovascular system, the endocrine system, and can lead to malignant tumors and premature death.* [11,13]

At the same time, lessons learned from the consequences of the Coronavirus pandemic have shown that most of the complications of disease and mortality are closely related to comorbidities caused by poor lifestyle. [7,8].

On this basis, we conducted a study among students of the Tashkent Medical Academy. The study aimed to improve the quality and effectiveness of student learning by "promoting a healthy lifestyle and principles of physical activity, improving health outcomes and eliminating health problems." [8]

Purpose of the topic: Improving the quality and effectiveness of student learning by "promoting a healthy lifestyle and the principles of physical activity, improving health indicators and eliminating health problems" among students of the Tashkent Medical Academy.

Materials and methods: The study was conducted both online and offline. Online survey conducted through this site "[questionnaire](#)". And offline viewing was conducted using a 12-

questionnaire prepared separately. the survey was conducted anonymously. The survey includes gender, ethnicity, place of residence, and some of the questions we need.

Research Process: 110 students voluntarily completed the questionnaire. We used the 6 most important questions in our study:

According to the results of answers to questions from the questionnaire:

First question: « What affects human health the most?» Heredity – 0%, doctors – 0%, environment – 0,6%, depends on the person and his lifestyle – 97,8%, other answers – 1,6% second question: « which of the following principles

will you follow in your lifestyle to improve your health?» Physical exercise – 33,5%, diet – 1%, walking – 56,8%, None of the listed – 8,4%, third question: « How regularly do you eat at the right time on a schedule? » 3-4 times a day: breakfast, lunch, dinner – 42,6%.

Regularly, but often without lunch (breakfast, dinner) – 10,3%, depends on situation – 45,6%, other answers – 1,5%, fourth question: « What is your physical activity while studying?» standing, with intense workouts – 5,9%, in a sitting position – 36,8%, in a mixed form – 57,3 fifth question: how long do you travel by public transport during the day? 10-20 minutes –

How regularly do you eat at the right time on a schedule?

- 3-4 times a day: breakfast, lunch, dinner
- Regularly, but often without lunch (breakfast, dinner)
- depends on situation
- other answers

23,5%, 30-40 minutes – 19,1%, one hour + - 30,9%, I hardly use public transport – 26,5%, Six question: « Are you doing work that requires physical activity?» Yes – 51,5%, No – 10,3%, Sometimes– 38,2%.

Conclusion: Based on the results of the surveys, the following were studied and analyzed: the levels of physical activity of students, the modes of food intake of students of the Tashkent

Medical Academy. But the results are not what we expected. Based on this, it is necessary to send students to recovery, constantly organize additional recreational activities. It is important that students properly organize their meals and follow the daily routine. We came to the conclusion that the prevention of physical inactivity and the prevention of diseases are relevant, and identified a number of tasks.

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